

From Supply Chain to Digital Ecosystem: Synchronizing Business Model Change during Digital Transformation

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ABSTRACT

This study explores how business model change is coordinated across firms during the digital transformation of a traditional supply chain into a digital ecosystem. Drawing on interdisciplinary research from the ecosystem literature in sociology, business model literature in management, and digital transformation literature in information systems, the purpose of this study is to provide theoretical insight into business model change during the digital transformation of a supply chain. Based on a ten-year longitudinal case of a beef farming supply chain, the study demonstrates that business model change unfolds through the intertwined dynamics of latency and emergence. Latency involves early-stage, non-economic groundwork, such as data infrastructure, trust-building, and standardized procedures, that lays the foundation for value propositions and future economic gains. Emergence captures the simultaneous, feedback-driven recalibrations of business models across interconnected actors as real-time data begins to synchronize decisions and operations. Using deductive theorizing grounded in the Gioia Method, the study reveals how business models of firms in a supply chain incrementally align with others to catalyze systemic change. Over time, data and derived intelligence becomes a strategic asset enabling new value creation, delivery, and capture mechanisms across the ecosystem. The findings extend traditional firm-centric and static views of business models, offering a dynamic, co-evolutionary perspective. This research contributes to the literature on digital transformation, business models, supply chain, and ecosystems by explaining how distributed, data-enabled coordination, rather than central control drives large-scale business model changes. The study provides theoretical and practical implications for managing digital transitions in complex, inter-organizational settings.

Keywords: Business Model Change, Digital transformation, Digital ecosystems, Supply Chains, Longitudinal Case study, Grounded Theory

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Abstract

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1. Introduction

The increasing pace of digital transformation (DT) is fundamentally reshaping how firms operate, collaborate, and compete, not only as standalone entities but as interdependent participants within broader, evolving ecosystems (Warner & Wäger, 2019; Volberda et al., 2021). As digital technologies such as IoT, cloud platforms, and advanced computing capabilities become embedded across organizational boundaries, they offer the potential to synchronize supply chain (SC) operations, improve visibility, and enhance responsiveness. Yet, systemic transformation often fails to materialize in the absence of corresponding shifts in how firms create, deliver, and capture value (Geurts & Cepa, 2023; Warner & Wäger, 2019). This signals that digital transformation is not merely a technological shift but a strategic and structural transition, one that necessitates the adaptation of business models in alignment with interconnected supply chain partners (Foss et al., 2023; Snihur & Bocken, 2022).

In the context of supply chains, the business model of a single firm cannot be examined in isolation, as supply chains operate as networks of interlinked firms whose coordinated business models collectively deliver value to end customers. Business models have traditionally been conceptualized as firm-level architectures of value creation, delivery, and capture (Teece, 2010; Zott et al., 2011). Managers have used them to respond to upstream and downstream changes by

reconfiguring internal processes and offerings. However, with increasing interdependence and the rise of real-time data integration, business models are increasingly being used as dynamic tools that shape interconnected trajectories, especially as firms seek to manage the complexity and volatility within digitally connected supply networks (Ivanov et al., 2022; Teece, 2018; Weking et al., 2020). This shift introduces the concept of collaborative complexity, which refers to “the joint creation of structures and processes by at least two organizations, enabling them to collectively respond to factors perceived as increasing complexity within their respective (and potentially overlapping) environments” (Schneider et al., 2017, pp. pp. 183 - 184). Despite the importance of this phenomenon, limited research exists on how firms jointly develop such complexity in response to digital transformation. In particular, there is a paucity of studies that examine how business model change (BMC) is coordinated across firms in multi-tiered chains (Adner, 2017; Hafeez et al., 2025).

Existing research on BMC and DT often emphasizes firm-centric, static perspectives (Teece, 2018), which fails to account for the collective, evolving nature of business model change within digitally transforming supply chains. Digital transformation has been shown to catalyze new routines and coordination mechanisms that span networks of suppliers, manufacturers, and customers laying the groundwork for the emergence of digital ecosystems (Dal Mas et al., 2024). These ecosystems are defined as “self-organizing, scalable, and sustainable systems comprising diverse digital entities and their interconnected relationships to enhance system utility, reaping benefits, and fostering internal and external information exchange” (Dal Mas et al., 2024). However, the processes by which business models co-evolve within such ecosystems remain under-investigated. The literature on digital ecosystems has primarily focused on mature platform industries (e.g., fintech, media) and often treats the ecosystem as a given state, with little attention to how these ecosystems emerge from traditional supply chains. The transformation process is particularly complex as it involves varying degrees of technological adoption, business process and function alteration, organizational alignment, and perceptual divergence among supply chain actors (D’Ippolito et al., 2019; Ivanov, 2024). During early stages of transformation, firms differ in how they perceive environmental changes and potential opportunities. However, these perceptual gaps begin to close as shared data, platforms, and visions for value creation are collectively embraced (Herterich et al., 2023).

In such scenarios, the focal firm often plays a catalytic role in initiating and coordinating change across the network. These actors harness digital infrastructures to align strategic trajectories and drive ecosystem-wide adaptations in value logic (Snihur et al., 2018). As supply chains digitalize and transition into digital ecosystems, the evidence of transformation becomes visible in changing business models (Ivanov et al., 2022), as in how firms reconfigure their activities, partnerships, and revenue mechanisms to reflect shared digital capabilities and objectives (Cozzolino et al., 2018; Weking et al., 2020). These changes signal not only firm-level shifts but also systemic reconfigurations in how value is co-created and distributed across the network. When digital technologies catalyze these shifts enabling real-time synchronization, data-sharing, and cross-organizational routines, the supply chain evolves into a cyber-physical digital ecosystem, where interorganizational linkages serve as conduits for system utility (Herterich et al., 2023; Magas & Kiritsis, 2022).

Despite the theoretical importance of this transition, we lack empirical studies that examine how business model adaptation is coordinated across firms during long-term digital transformation in traditional supply chains. Addressing this gap is critical for developing a more integrated understanding of DT that spans the domains of supply chain management, strategy, information

systems, and ecosystem theory. Therefore, drawing on these streams of literature we extend the study of business models by broadening its scope from an individual firm's business model to an entire supply chain and aim to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: How is business model change coordinated across firms during digital transformation of a supply chain?

RQ2: What are the underlying mechanisms that synchronize business model changes to facilitate a digital ecosystem?

To answer these research questions we empirically explore a 10-year digital transformation of a traditional agricultural supply chain of beef cattle. Using focus groups, semi structured interviews, archival reports and observations we track the transition of a traditional farm and its supply chain into a digital ecosystem through business model change from 2014 - 2024. These ten years of data are analyzed using deductive theorizing and the Gioia Method (Gehman et al., 2018; Gioia et al., 2013). Our analysis leads to a conceptual framework that identifies Latency and emergence as distinct yet interrelated underlying mechanisms that lead to ecosystem formation during digitalization of supply chains.

The contributions of this study are fourfold. First, it offers a dynamic, temporal perspective on how digitally enabled supply chain ecosystems unfold, moving beyond static or single-firm analyses to show transformation as an evolving, multi-actor process. Second, the study introduces the conceptual duality of latency and emergence, demonstrating that early non-economic investments such as data infrastructure, interoperable routines, and trust-building are foundational for later economic synchronization and value capture across the network. Third, it shows that these latent, invisible investments are necessary precursors to the visible phases of coordinated change, thereby advancing understanding of how digital transformation cascades across interconnected firms. Fourth, the study contributes to the business model literature by segregating business model change at the firm level from business model change at the ecosystem level, revealing how individual firms' adaptations unify into system-wide reconfiguration. Collectively, these contributions enrich digital transformation scholarship and offer a more holistic explanation of how supply chains transition into data-driven ecosystems.

The outline for the remainder of this paper is as follows. Section 2 entails the conceptual background of the study describing each concept in detail followed by Section 3 of Methodology. Section 4 describes the analysis and findings of the study and section 6 provides a discussion on those insights. Section 7 entails the managerial implications while section 8 discusses the limitations and future research directions for the study.

2. CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Digital Transformation in Supply Chains

Digital transformation (DT) has become a central concept in operations and supply chain management, generally referring to the use of new digital technologies to enable major business improvements and streamline operations and processes (Aslam et al., 2025) through the exchange of supply chain related information within and across its boundaries (Dal Mas et al., 2024; Hafeez et al., 2025; Ivanov, 2024). Most studies on digital transformation focus on the individual firm

(Björkdahl, 2020; Hafeez et al., 2025; Snihur & Bocken, 2022), along with their processes (Ghobakhloo, 2020; Warner & Wäger, 2019) and functional departments as the unit of analysis. Over the past few decades, supply chains have undergone a profound evolution driven by data-centric technologies that not only improve interorganizational coordination but also drive the reconfiguration of supply chains at the strategic, tactical and operational levels (Ivanov et al., 2022). These technologies create an integrated information infrastructure, allowing multiple independent actors to operate in sync and respond rapidly to changes. Belhadi et al. (2024) observe that data-driven digital initiatives end up embedded in the strategic, structural, and procedural facets of SC management, influencing long-term decisions about network design, sourcing, and market positioning. Operationally, DT demands redesigning processes to be more flexible, real-time, and information-rich. It is not a mere adjustment of a few workflows, but often a fundamental reengineering of the business models of the firms and how their supply chain operates day-to-day.

Unlike traditional IT-enabled changes that optimize existing processes, true DT entails redefining an organization's value proposition and sometimes its identity, fundamentally reshaping structures and practices rather than just layering technology on top. To understand this in context of supply chain transformation a more granular understanding is needed as to how DT cascades throughout the chain. The supply chain DT does not happen in isolation; it intertwines with changes in how a firm does business and how it engages a wider ecosystem of partners. Traditional arms-length, transactional relationships translate into deeper partnerships characterized by high levels of trust, transparency, and information exchange (Yu et al., 2023; Zhou et al., 2023). Sharing sensitive data or integrating systems across organizational boundaries requires partners to have confidence in each other's security and intent. Zhang et al. (2025) demonstrate this in multi-tier supply chains where the DT initiatives from focal firms diffuse down to second-tier suppliers and hinges on the strength of trust and shared vision between the tiers. Firms leverage data-driven technologies to transform not only internal operations but the very logic of how they create and deliver value, moving beyond the linear, siloed supply chain models of the past.

Ivanov et al. (2022) echoes the same notion naming it the multi structural dynamics of supply chains. They mention supply chain as a combination of different organizational, information, financial and processes structures, and state that change in one can trigger changes in all other structures. Due to uncertainties and resulting initiatives like digitalization these structures do not remain static rather they reconfigure, evolve and are dynamic in nature (Dolgui et al., 2020). The existing literature has mainly considered these structures as static and fails to grasp the complete picture of the dynamic aspect. In context of DT, the information structure is of prime importance as it drives change in the other structures. Though Ivanov et al. (2022) and Dolgui et al. (2020) lay the groundwork for these supply chain structures, yet the changing dynamics and how the structures intertwine and evolve overtime in harmony requires exploration. In this regard, adopting a business model lens serves as a valuable analytical perspective. Supply chains can be viewed as collections of interdependent firms, each operating their own business model, yet collectively delivering value to the end customer. As DT reshapes operations, the value proposition, creation and capture mechanisms require a fundamental reinvention of business

models across the chain (Sengupta et al., 2021). In this sense, supply chain DT is not merely a process upgrade; it is a reconfiguration of a network of interconnected business models, where shifts in one actor's value proposition or processes ripple across others.

Despite the evident interlinkage of supply chains and their constituent business models, studies at the intersection of both literature remains scarce. Current supply chain research has only partially incorporated the business model lens to explain how such transformations unfold (Ivanov et al., 2022), while much of the strategy literature on digital business models overlooks their supply chain-wide implications and interdependencies (Li et al., 2025). Bridging these perspectives is essential to understand how Business Model Change (BMC) and cross-firm coordination jointly drive value creation. The next section builds on this insight by examining BMC within digital transformation contexts. This transition from a focus on supply chain processes to business model evolution will shed light on the firm-level strategies that enable and result from successful digital transformation in supply chains.

2.2 Digital Transformation and Business Model Change

The average business model lifespan has reportedly shrunk from 15 to 5 years in recent decades, due to rapid entry of new players and disruptive offerings (BCG, 2025). Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) provide one of the most widely cited definitions of a business model, characterizing it as "the rationale of how an organization creates, delivers, and captures value." Business models thus play a critical role in enabling firms to exploit opportunities through the strategic configuration of their activities (Zott & Amit, 2010). However, over time, it has become more important for business models to serve as a framework for understanding how firms function at operational and systemic levels (Magretta, 2002; Snihur & Markman, 2023). Chesbrough (2007) argues that a business model is not merely a strategic tool but also an innovative tool, enabling companies to explore and exploit new business opportunities. With the rapid diffusion and advancements of digital technologies, the concept of a business model has garnered significant attention, particularly as individual firms increasingly recognize the importance of aligning their strategic, operational, and financial activities to create value in digital environments. In this way, the business model can bridge between strategy and operations, articulating a system of activities that generate competitive advantage (Teece, 2010; Zott & Amit, 2010). To pursue and sustain this competitive advantage organizations opt for BMC for growth and to defend against industry disruption by novel technologies or competitors (Sengupta et al., 2021). BMC is defined as 'changes to the key elements of a firm's business model and the architecture linking these elements' (Foss & Saebi, 2017). At its core, a business model describes how a firm creates value - a process that allows firms to generate revenue streams while simultaneously managing costs (Snihur & Markman, 2023; Teece, 2010).

Multiple studies identify technological and environmental shifts as primary drivers of BMC (Snihur & Markman, 2023; Teece, 2018; Weking et al., 2020). The advent of digitalization has created strong pressure for firms to redesign their business models where digital technologies are not only transforming operational processes but also reshaping the very architecture of value

creation and delivery, prompting scholars to explore how business models must adapt accordingly. Ivanov et al. (2022) introduce the concept of the “cloud supply chain”, a novel business model that leverages cloud platforms and Industry 4.0 technologies to offer Supply-Chain-as-a-Service. This model relies on networking third-party assets through digital platforms, illustrating how new technology can enable fundamentally different value creation structures. Similarly, Weking et al. (2020) note that manufacturing firms must innovate their business models (e.g. via servitization, cloud manufacturing, platform models) to exploit Industry 4.0, which has often been treated purely as a technological change. In fact, failing to adapt the business model to digital opportunities can jeopardize a firm’s survival. Li et al. (2025) provide empirical evidence that digitalization forces firms to rethink their business model design as information no longer flows linearly, but in networks, necessitating fundamental changes to the firm’s business models to align with digital supply chain systems. They identify that firms struggle to realize benefits from new technologies until they adjust their business models, highlighting digitalization as a catalyst for BMC. Overall, emerging technologies (IoT, AI, cloud platforms) act as a major driver of BMC, pushing firms toward more connected, data-driven, and service-oriented models. These insights underscore that BMC is not merely a firm-level response to digitalization but a mechanism that fundamentally reshapes how supply chains function and evolve, paving the way for understanding how digitally connected business models interact to form broader supply chain ecosystems.

2.3 Digital Transformation and Ecosystems

Digital transformation can be conceptualized along a continuum of technological depth (Gillani et al., 2024; Tekic et al., 2024). From incremental “shallow” transformation through localized technologies, to “deep” transformation that leverages core technologies such as IoT, AI, and cloud platforms to reshape industries and their architectures to form ecosystems. While shallow DT has been widely studied and dominates literature, research on how deep DT transforms businesses, their supply chains and architectures remains limited. Crucially, deep supply chain DT reconfigures patterns of coordination, data sharing, and interdependence across firms, creating the conditions under which digital ecosystems emerge. These ecosystems are complex, adaptive networks of self-organizing, scalable, and sustainable systems where multiple firms collaborate, co-create value, and synchronize decisions through shared digital infrastructure (Dal Mas et al., 2024). These ecosystems thrive on data-driven interdependence, where the integration of technologies across firm boundaries facilitates collective responsiveness, agility, and innovation (Hafeez et al., 2025; Herterich et al., 2023). Wu et al. (2024) highlight the supply chain data network effect, where digitally connected partners generate compounding returns by contributing data and learnings that benefit the entire network. This transforms traditional linear supply chains into digital platform ecosystems, capable of orchestrating coordination and developing shared capabilities that no single firm could achieve alone (Geissbauer et al., 2020). Such transformation necessitates a shift in unit of analysis: from the individual firm to the network. As ecosystems evolve, they demand new structures and processes in response to shared complexity of deeper

collaboration, real-time data exchange, and aligned incentives across actors (Schneider et al., 2017).

To coordinate value creation and collaboration platforms are used as an effective orchestrating mechanism. Platforms enable alignment, visibility, and coordination among interdependent actors (Geurts & Cepa, 2023; Ivanov et al., 2022; Li & Schoenherr, 2023) and act as the structural and technological backbone of these ecosystems. Platforms facilitate alignment, visibility, and orchestration across interdependent actors by enabling seamless data exchange, process integration, and stakeholder interaction (Khanagha et al., 2022; Rantala et al., 2023). (Cusumano et al., 2020) note that platform-based business models derive value through network effects where the addition of each user enhances the value for all participants. These platforms also help orchestrate BMC, as firms align their value propositions, operations, and customer engagement strategies with the requirements and expectations of the broader ecosystem (Snihur et al., 2021). Gawer and Cusumano (2014) explain that such ecosystem evolution is embedded in modifications to products, processes, organizations, and even industry architectures. In this way, the digital transformation of supply chains is no longer confined to isolated process improvements, it represents a systemic reconfiguration of how value is created, delivered, and captured across a network of actors often orchestrated through platforms.

3. Methodology and Research Design

We employ a longitudinal case study methodology, with 10 years of data, to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the business model change and ecosystem formation during digital transformation of a supply chain (Abdallah et al., 2011; Yin, 2009). This approach follows the work of Jacobides et al. (2018) suggesting that ecosystem emergence can be tested by longitudinal research. It allows for an in-depth examination of the multi-level (i.e., micro and macro) evolutionary patterns, adaptations, and embedded practices particularly within digital ecosystems, shedding light on how these sophisticated systems develop, sustain, and enhance their capabilities over time. Not only does this approach reveal divergences in each firm's perceptions of the environment (Boyd et al., 1993), but also is helpful in developing theories from case study observations, especially for underdeveloped domains. It caters for the unique contextualized understanding of the concept and associated linkages (Eisenhardt, 1989; Li & Schoenherr, 2023; Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

Focusing on a beef farming supply chain in Mainland China, this study unearths the mechanisms through which digital transformation gives rise to an ecosystem and theorizes the role of business model change in shaping and synchronizing this process. Between 2014 and 2024, we engaged with more than 15 stakeholder groups of KN (the lead company) including early adopters, operational enablers, strategic partners, and institutional actors involved in the transformation and scaling of the ecosystem. The context of this region is interesting to study as it is the second-largest consumer of beef in the world and has seen a 50% increase in consumption in the last decade. The per capita consumption is estimated to increase by another 10% by 2031 (FAO, 2022). Furthermore, being one of the fastest growing economies, China has advanced well in

technological proficiency and accelerated application and scaling of advanced technologies in different industries, including beef related ones. In addition, the beef supply chain contains products (i.e. live cattle, feed, beef) and services (i.e. vaccination, logistics), that cannot be fully digitized, presenting a highly valuable and complex context to investigate.

Data Collection

Data from KN and its partners was collected using focus groups, semi-structured interviews and field observations as they allow an in-depth exploration of participants' experiences and opinions during digital transformation of the supply chain to a digital ecosystem (Qazi et al., 2018). Data collection took place from September 2014 to September 2024, where two of the researchers of this article acted as independent external observers of the digital transformation. Over the ten-year study period, 19 focus groups (FG) and 35 semi-structured interviews were conducted. Each FG was structured around a clearly defined transformation agenda. These agendas were aligned with KN's evolving strategic roadmap and targeted the specific supply chain components undergoing change. In most years, two focus groups were convened; one in January and one in September, to capture both the initiation and consolidation of transformation efforts, thereby enabling longitudinal tracking of supply chain and business model evolution. The interviews were conducted with the main leads of KN and their partners at different points over the years. This gave us a diverse perspective of how transformation was progressing at different fronts and how changes at all fronts were coinciding to reconfigure the supply chain into a digitally coordinated ecosystem. Details of the respondents, focus groups and interviews are shown in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Focus Group	Agenda	Year	Role in Company	Role in Supply Chain	Duration
FG1	Self-owned farm/flagship KN farm	Sep 2014	CEO	Feed 1	150 min
FG2		Jan 2015	CEO CFO CEO Director	KN Farm Feed 1 DT installation Feed 2	
FG3	Scaling smart farms	Sep 2015	CEO	Feed 1	80 min
FG4		Jan 2016	CEO CFO CEO CEO	KN Farm Feed DT installation Farm 1 Farm 2	
FG5	High end product differentiation	Sep 2016	CEO	Feed 1	90 min
FG6		Jan 2017	CEO CEO CEO Director Head Trading platform	Farm 3 DT installation Health provider ² Feed 2 Online trading	
FG7	Offline trading	Sep 2017	CEO CEO CEO	Feed 1 Farm Trading	120 min

FG8		Jan 2018	CEO Head Head Trading Platform	Abattoir Logistics Online Trading	98 min
FG9	Trading of breeding cows	Sep 2018	CEO	Feed 1	115 min
FG10		Jan 2019	CEO CFO Import-export partner	Trading Feed 1 Farm/product	120 min
FG11	Online trading of DT enabled cows	Sep 2019	CEO	Feed 1	50 min
FG12		Jan 2020	CEO CEO CEO Head	Trading Online trading Farm 2 Logistics	84 min
FG13	DT based smart farm infrastructure	Sep 2020	CEO	KN	140 min
FG14		Jan 2021	CEO CEO CEO CEO Director CEO Manager	Online Trading DT Installation KN farm Construction Company Feed 2 Genetics/Health Trading	
FG15	Online trading between DT- BFSC network	Sep 2021	CEO	KN	45 min
FG16		Jan 2022	CEO Director CEO CEO Head	KN farm Feed 2 Genetic/Health Farm 1 Logistics	90 min
FG17	Traders network – 2- sided market & logistics	Sep 2022	CEO	KN farm	75 min
FG18		Jan 2023	CEO CEO CEO Head	Farm 3 Trading Online trading Logistics	
FG19	Data Monetization and partnerships	Sep 2024	CEO CEO Manager data analytics Head of Logistics CEO CEO CEO	KN farm KN Local authority Logistics Trading Construction Company	120 min

Table 1: Details of respondents and focus groups conducted

Respondent Type	Organizational Affiliation	Role in Supply Chain	Years in Industry	Number of Interviews	Time Period
CEO	KN	Lead innovator; Focal firm	>20	9	2015 - 2024
CEO	Genetics/Health Operators	Standardized genetics and growth practices using KN data services	>5	2	2016 – 2017
CEO	Feed 1	Partner firm in feed trading Joint Ventures	>10	2	2016 – 2017

CEO	KN Farm	Developed and franchised digital smart farm of KN	>20	5	2016 – 2022
CFO	Feed 2	Feed suppliers for KN	>20	1	2018
Head of R&D	KN	Developed IP, ran flagship labs, standardized protocols	>10	4	2016 – 2021
CEO	Tech installation	Responsible for embedding and installing digital technologies throughout the farm	>10	4	2017 – 2021
CEO	Cattle Traders	Independent Traders/ Platform Users	>30	2	2019
CEO	Beverage Company Executive	Co-invested in high-end dairy farms producing value-added products	>20	1	2022
Head of Logistics	Logistics	Co-designed smart transportation solutions for cattle	>10	2	2019
CEO	Construction Company	Built and modified farm infrastructure for smart farming	>5	3	2018 - 2023

Table 2: Details of interviews conducted

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed in three rounds following the Gioia Method (Gehman et al., 2018; Gioia et al., 2013). Reflecting on the research questions, the authors cyclically consulted with the data, the business model literature, the digital transformation literature, and the ecosystem (and digital ecosystem) literature to develop the proposed framework.

The focus groups and interviews were transcribed verbatim, and the first stage began with open coding of the respondent’s perceptions of business model change. This yielded first-order respondent-centric codes derived from the changes from each business model change that occurred from one time period to the next (Abdallah et al., 2011) as shown in Table 3. In the second stage, axial coding revealed second-order codes derived from the overall change during the digital transformation of a supply chain to a digital ecosystem (Coffey & Atkinson, 1996) as shown in Table 4. There were nine second order codes which demonstrate a higher level of abstraction. During stage three, data analysis consisted of reconciling the data with existing theory to create an overall framework that explains business model change during the digital transformation of a supply chain into a digital ecosystem (Gioia et al., 2013). From this, the first and second order codes were collapsed into two main drivers of business model change: latency and emergence. Notably, these two drivers were derived from codes generated from micro-level data i.e. firm level data, as well as codes generated from macro-level data i.e. the ecosystem level data. Because of this, together the codes that comprise the proposed framework represent different levels of the ecosystem. These are described in the tables below, and illustrated in Figures 1 - 4. Detailed changes and transformation aspects are shown in Appendix A. To verify data analysis and to confirm trustworthiness of the results, the researchers consulted with one another at each stage of coding. Moreover, they evaluated whether and how the results aligned with extant theory. Discrepancies were addressed through discussion (Yin, 2009).

4. FINDINGS

4.1 Context - Beef Farming Supply Chain Transformation

Beef farming in China, like in many emerging markets, has traditionally operated within fragmented and inefficient supply chains, marked by intuition-based trading, low traceability, and limited integration (Malafaia et al., 2021) across upstream (breeding, feeding, healthcare), midstream (farming operations), and downstream (logistics, abattoirs, and distribution) stages. These legacy systems are predominantly offline, manual, and data-poor, leading to poor coordination, opaque practices, and disproportionate power dynamics, often favouring abattoirs and traders over farmers. As a result, transparency is minimal, and value distribution remained highly unequal.

Each stage of the beef farming supply chain is crucial to cattle growth. The upstream stage ensures feed and healthcare quality leading to better cattle growth and survival. The midstream stage centres on the beef farm, responsible for animal well-being, growth monitoring, and key trading decisions. The downstream includes logistics, abattoir operations, and market distribution, where stress during transportation and poor slaughterhouse coordination can compromise beef quality and lead to economic losses for farmers (Singh et al., 2015). Historically, beef farmers struggled with high calf mortality, poor access to veterinary services, and limited know-how about breed selection and animal healthcare (Mota et al., 2023). These inefficiencies forced farmers to reinvest in more cattle just to stay afloat, undermining their economic sustainability. At the same time, seasonal employment, low margins, and information asymmetries left farmers socially and financially vulnerable, while other value chain actors reaped greater profits. Moreover, the lack of epidemic control, minimal immunization, and rudimentary transportation practices further affected beef quality and reduced consumer trust.

This landscape began to shift with the intervention of KN Group, the focal firm that initiated a strategic digital transformation starting with a self-owned flagship smart farm. Over the next decade (2014–2024), this evolved into a multi-actor, digitally synchronized ecosystem, connecting breeders, feed providers, farmers, traders, logistics providers, abattoirs and even healthcare actors through shared digital infrastructure, real-time data, and platform-based coordination mechanisms. The transformation replaced siloed, peer-to-peer interactions with a cohesive, data-driven network. As this digitally coordinated network unfolded over time, the transformation did not progress linearly or uniformly; rather, it was characterized by distinct yet interrelated patterns that governed how business models adapted and how the ecosystem ultimately took shape. A brief glimpse of the timeline of activities over the ten years is shown in Table 3.

Year	Activity
2014	KN sensing inefficiencies and exploratory experimentation initiated. KN begins scanning loopholes in traditional beef farming and identifying opportunities for data-driven coordination and digital reconfiguration.
2015	Early digital experimentation and cross-industry learning. Informal transfer of digital practices from dairy to beef farming begins, focusing on animal growth monitoring and basic pedigree tracking.
2016	Industry hopping formalized: systematic migration of digital practices from dairy farms to beef farms. Foundational digital infrastructure established for cattle pedigree, growth monitoring, and maintenance of biological records.

2017	Initial datafication of farm operations. Feeding, consumption, and health data collection routines introduced. Manual digital twin records piloted across selected partner farms, extending DT beyond the focal farm
2018	Physical–digital restructuring of farms. Built environment redesigned to support sensor-based monitoring and data capture, marking the transition from isolated DT pilots to embedded digital infrastructure
2019	Integrated value chain digitalization achieved. Breed-specific feeding based on biological data introduced; full cattle lifecycle records established. Survival rates exceed 90%. New trading standards (e.g., 4-month benchmark) introduced. Formation of a specialized smart farm construction entity signals ecosystem role differentiation Online multi-sided trading platform launched, enabling earlier-stage cattle trading and broader market participation.
2020	Shift from operational digitization to platform coordination. Preventive healthcare routines embedded. Standardized smart beef farming training offered as a service. Big data services initiated.
2021	Financial ecosystem integration - Digital tech–based asset securitization introduced. Banks recognize cattle as data-backed financial assets, enabling loans and external capital inflows into the ecosystem.
2022	Ecosystem modularization and scaling. Smart Farming as a Service (SFaaS) expanded. R&D decoupled from operations. Breed-specific precision livestock farming (PLF) routines standardized and replicated across farms.
2023	Productivity-driven healthcare optimization. Advanced data analytics used to fine-tune intervention timing (e.g., snipping), enhancing yield and operational efficiency across large-scale farms D2C ¹ channels initiated – retail outlets established to offer high grade quality beef (A3) for fine dining
2024	Ecosystem consolidation and maturation. Large-scale smart farm operations exceed 10,000 cattle. KN operates as an ecosystem orchestrator, coordinating production, data services, finance, training, and standards across the network.

Table 3: Chronological order of activities for ecosystem emergence

Our findings reveal **latency** and **emergence** as recurring, interlinked patterns shaping the digital transformation of the supply chain into an ecosystem. Latency reflects the initiatives taken to establish the foundational infrastructures without immediate economic returns that cumulatively lay the groundwork for transformation. In parallel, emergence describes the economic recalibrations simultaneously experienced across the supply chain. In the sections that follow, each pattern is first traced temporally through the sequence of events and then examined as a construct, outlining its theoretical antecedents and consequences.

¹ Direct to Consumer

4.2 Latency - as it occurs temporally

In the early stages (T0 – T2), latency starts from the identification of systemic inefficiencies that existed throughout the supply chain and the creation of a shared database and foundational digital design principles. For instance, at T0, KN realizes the issues with power asymmetries existing among stakeholders due to intuitive decision making of traders and abattoirs which would put farmers at a disadvantage. The fragmented supply chain with lack of (accurate) information flow was offset by the creation of a shared data repository containing cattle pedigree, biometrics, and growth tracking information. Although the upfront investment increased immediate costs without clear short-term profitability yet laid the groundwork for predictive healthcare and standardized trading. As the theoretical grounding emphasizes, these foundational steps demonstrate how latency creates essential but subtle changes that later enable economic shifts.

Between T3 and T4, latency is reinforced through incremental improvements: data-enabled healthcare models, QR-based vaccinations, and evidence-based trading replace intuitive, relationship-bound decision-making. As data became widely available and reliable across stakeholders, latent improvements in the transparency and efficiency of trading emerged at T3. For instance, cattle records shared through the digital platform gradually shifted trade decisions from intuitive judgments toward evidence-based trading, reshaping relationships and power dynamics among farmers, traders, and abattoirs. Notably, this change was incremental and not initially economically driven; instead, it reflected a latency-based transition toward routinized digital trading practices, thus preparing the ecosystem for subsequent economic recalibration. These changes altered the value proposition (from intuition to data-based services) and key processes (digitized transactions) without immediate shifts in value capture.

From T4 to T6, standardized data-informed feeding practices (T4), establishment of feed-trading joint ventures (T4b), and smart logistics partnerships (T5) emerged. These initiatives did not yield immediate profits; instead strengthened relational capital across the chain and aligned operational standards but still prioritized ecosystem cohesion over immediate revenue growth.

Between T7 and T9, latency reappears as the ecosystem entered its scaling phase. Partnerships with construction and digital technology installation firms to design smart farm infrastructure, the formalization of joint ventures for farm franchising, and the development of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) with mobile training teams expanded the ecosystem's key resources and codified its processes. These initiatives prioritized interoperability, trust, and capability building before direct monetization.

By T9, these latent foundations enabled new revenue-oriented services, such as Smart Farming as a Service (SFaaS), and strategic partnerships with dairy and breeding farms demonstrating how non-economic, preparatory shifts underpin subsequent business model transformation.

In sum, latency consistently provided the structural, relational, and institutional groundwork necessary for subsequent economic and business model changes, reinforcing theoretical propositions around latency as a period of unexpected and indirect adjustments critical to later ecosystem developments.

4.3 Latency - as a construct

Antecedents – Establishing Shared Digital Foundations (T0 to T2)

Latency originates in the recognition of systemic inefficiencies and fragmentation in the beef farming supply chain (T0). The focal firm (KN) initiated shared digital infrastructure by creating

a centralised cattle pedigree database and establishing digital design principles (T2). Early business model changes among individual actors were prompted by access to this shared authenticated data, which empowered them to improve processes without directly altering value capture. For example, healthcare providers adopted data-driven routines, including QR-based vaccination systems (T3), while traders and abattoirs shifted from intuition-led decision-making to evidence-based trading underpinned by real-time cattle health and growth data (T2).

Mechanisms – Building Trust, Relational Exchange, and Mutuality (T2 to T5)

As digital practices routinised, the trading platform was developed (T3), enabling participation by multiple chain actors. This platform-based model facilitated trust, strengthened relational exchange, and fostered mutuality between stakeholders. Business model changes reflected shifts in value proposition (from product to service orientation) and key processes (from manual to data-optimised). Feed suppliers became strategic partners by offering customized, data-optimised feed (T4), and KN formalised its role through a feed-trading venture (T4). Similarly, partnerships with logistics firms to create smart trucks that reduced cattle stress during transport (T5) represented investments for operational alignment, standardisation, and quality assurance.

Consequences – Streamlining the Value Chain and Enabling Synchronisation (T6 to T9)

By the scaling phase, latency manifested in initiatives that consolidated and extended operational capabilities across the network. Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for smart farms were developed (T8), alongside the deployment of mobile technical teams to support cross-farm adoption. Partnerships expanded beyond beef farming into dairy farms (T8) and breeding farms (T8), integrating new data-driven practices into these domains. These actions streamlined the value chain, enhancing compatibility between diverse farming models and creating a pool of shared capabilities. The introduction of Smart Farming as a Service (SFaaS) (T9) marked the readiness for monetisation; a step made possible only because latency had created the structural, relational, and operational preconditions for ecosystem-wide synchronisation.

In a nutshell, latency is both a pattern and a process: a recurring, non-economic phase where shared data, trust-based relationships, and aligned operations are cultivated. These latent outcomes are critical precursors to the synchronised business model changes and monetisation strategies that ultimately define the mature digital ecosystem.

The economic recalibration for the beef farming supply chain continuously happened through the real time data synchronization and the bidirectional exchange of this data to improve processes and decision making. It initiated with a macro-analysis of the environment (T-2) by KN, to identify the inefficiencies of the current farming practices. To mitigate these inefficiencies and to improve product quality a shared database on cattle pedigree was generated which improved healthcare checks for the cattle, developed information systems for data sharing among partners and facilitate data driven healthcare routines. The data-driven business model changes in healthcare and farm resulted in system level improvements which rippled improvements that simultaneously occur across multiple actors in the ecosystem, triggering additional business model adaptations. Figure 1 shows the coding for latency.

Insert Figure 1 here

4.4 Emergence – as it occurs temporally

As data-driven transformations reshape supply chain relationships, the formation of partnerships and joint ventures marks the transition from isolated BMC to the formation of an interconnected digital ecosystem. The findings reveal a distinct pattern of economically sustaining actions across the ecosystem, which we conceptualize as *emergence*. At T1, initial system-level improvements in cattle healthcare, catalyzed by real-time genetic and biometric data, set off ripple effects across the wider supply chain. These healthcare gains, such as early disease detection and optimized treatment schedules, quickly translated into measurable improvements in cattle growth rates and condition. By T2–T4, the benefits had diffused into adjacent processes, with trading, feeding, and wholesaling becoming more transparent, standardized, and economically efficient. This rapid propagation of operational enhancements across interdependent actors illustrates *emergence*: changes initiated in one domain catalyze parallel adjustments throughout the ecosystem.

By T5, these cumulative improvements in productivity and beef quality increased the market appeal of participating farms, drawing in new external stakeholders, most notably non-KN farms keen to capture the same cattle growth rates and economic gains. Their entry further expanded the platform’s trading volumes and enriched the shared data repository, reinforcing positive network effects and aligning incentives across the ecosystem.

Subsequent economic recalibrations became even more explicit from T6 onward. The expansion of smart farm infrastructure (T6), the franchising of the KN model to other farms (T7), and SFaaS initiatives (T9) represent emergence-driven processes of economic recalibration. Each step clearly created ripple effects across the ecosystem, recalibrating economic activities and attracting additional capital and stakeholders. For instance, by T9, banks and investors recognized the digital replica of cattle in terms of data records as a legitimate financial assets, thus economically legitimizing and financially underpinning further ecosystem expansions.

The later stages (T8–T10) showcased how emergence led stakeholders to capitalize on and monetize the increasing availability and quality of ecosystem data. By T10, KN began offering comprehensive data-driven standards and solutions to external authorities and governmental bodies, further economically recalibrating the ecosystem. These emergence-driven monetization strategies demonstrated how earlier latent infrastructure investments in data and collaboration directly translated into substantial economic benefits and strategic differentiation, reinforcing the theoretical grounding of emergence as economically synchronized recalibration.

4.5 Emergence – as a construct

Emergence describes the process of simultaneous and continuous economic recalibration in which digitally enabled improvements in one part of the supply chain trigger parallel adaptations across interconnected actors, creating diversified revenue streams. This phenomenon is marked by the orchestration of diverse actors, the institutionalization of diversified revenue streams, and the scaling of platform-wide coordination through real-time, standardized data (Daymond et al., 2023; Jacobides et al., 2018). While latency reflects the groundwork of shared trust, digital infrastructure,

and process realignment, emergence captures the inflection point where these shifts collectively give rise to ecosystem-level transformation, supported by recursive feedback loops of innovation and monetization.

Antecedents – Systemic synchronization through data

Driven by enhanced transparency across the processes of feeding, healthcare wholesaling and abattoirs (T2-T4) across the supply chain, the cattle growth rate improved. This resulted in high-grade beef that enabled value capture through superior quality and product differentiation. Given these improvements, the digital ecosystem expanded further with non-KN farms joining the platform. This expansion not only enriched data repository for variants of beef types from different farms but also increased trading through the platform (T5). The KN farms started scaling, which necessitated the need to develop partnerships with construction companies and digital technology installation companies that helped modify farms to smart ones (T6). The inter- and intra-industry collaborations based on shared data developed an intricate web of data-driven interdependent linkages, regulated by the platform, improved the return on investment for all firms in the ecosystem.

Mechanisms – Strategic Ecosystem Scaling

The strategic ecosystem scaling is depicted by three components, Product Differentiation and Value Capture, ecosystem scaling through partner inclusion and modular replication of value models. The adoption of data-informed practices led to demonstrable improvements in cattle quality and consistency. The result was higher-grade beef that met stringent buyer expectations, allowing KN and participating farms to differentiate their products in the marketplace. This product differentiation translated into premium pricing, repeat demand, and strengthened brand positioning. These economic gains encouraged deeper commitment to smart farming technologies and incentivised others to join the ecosystem.

External actors, most notably non-KN farms (T5), entered the platform. Their participation not only increased trading volumes but also enriched the data pool. To accommodate scaling needs, partnerships were formed with construction firms and digital technology installation firms (T6) to physically upgrade conventional farms into smart farming environments. This enabled scalable, repeatable integration of new actors without diluting ecosystem coherence.

The emergence of modular, replicable value structures allowed for scalable economic expansion. The franchising of the KN farm model (T7) enabled geographic and operational replication. In parallel, KN launched Smart Farming as a Service (SFaaS, T9) to train labour for smart operations, thereby monetizing knowledge assets. Additional collaborations with dairy producers (T9 – T10) enabled premium co-branded dairy lines, diversifying revenue while leveraging existing infrastructure.

Consequences – Institutional Validation and Data Monetization

The cumulative result of emergence was the transformation of KN's operating model from one dependent on cattle trading to a multi-stream economic engine. Revenue sources now included trading fees, feed margins, logistics coordination, franchising royalties, training income, data-as-a-service, standards certification, and IP licensing. Simultaneously, ecosystem-level capital

inflows from banks and public sector partners enabled infrastructure expansion and firm-level resilience. KN was repositioned as a platform orchestrator, offering not only operational coordination but also regulatory solutions, standards, and market shaping capabilities. Ultimately, the strengthened engagement among ecosystem stakeholders fostered increased resource availability and enhanced capabilities, creating a self-sustaining cycle of BMC, efficiency, and market expansion.

Insert Figure 2 here

5. DISCUSSION

Drawing from literatures on supply chains, ecosystem and digital transformation, this study unearths how digital transformation of supply chains evolves into digital ecosystems through layered and synchronized business model changes. The underlying connotation for ecosystem formation is common among these literatures and calls for understanding how digital transformation gives rise to new inter-organizational ecosystems. In particular, our study addresses (Foss et al., 2023) call for exploring the processes that might play a role in ecosystem formation as opposed to exploring the intricacies of established ecosystems. We also address the research gaps mentioned by Adner (2017), Volberda et al. (2021) and Geurts and Cepa (2023) who posit that digitalization leads to ecosystem formation through changes in industrial architectures and new forms of organizations such as platformization, yet we lack clarity on *when and how* such ecosystem-level transformations occur. Furthermore, the literature suggests that digital transformation demands not only technical upgrades but also novel business models and partnership logics which require an exploration of how such business model changes unfold and pave the way for ecosystem formation (Weking et al., 2020). This study sheds light on the aforementioned gaps and identifies latency and emergence as the two parallel processes that shape multi-actor networks enabled by new technologies.

By tracing the longitudinal transformation of KN's beef supply chain, we reveal that ecosystem formation is neither spontaneous nor linear, rather it unfolds through the dynamic interplay of latency and emergence which coordinate BMC. First, latency - or, unexpected effects that do not follow economic principles lay the groundwork for ecosystem emergence and the interlinked individual firms that adopt new technologies slowly become calibrated to one another in the supply chain (Wagner, 2021). The firms ultimately become synchronized and complementary toward one another in ways that do not follow typical economic principles. As a result, the findings show that the focal firm displays its own proposed business model to other firms in the supply chain, and intentionally but incrementally designs or adapts its activities to nurture further integration of the proposed business model with those of chain partners (Snihur et al., 2018). Second, an emergence - or, a set of feed-backward and feed-forward loops that occur simultaneously enable business model change that radiates outward to other business models in a supply chain. In this way, the emergence catalyzes change in both previously revised business models as well as yet-to-be revised business models of chain partners. Newly developed routines and operations, across the supply chain incrementally change with each emergence during a digital transformation, thereby spanning the micro-macro divide (Aguinis et al., 2011; Li et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the results also suggest that there is no single firm that controls business model change in a supply chain. The focal firm facilitates the change, and instead, the latency and emergence of each BMC coordinates other business model changes across the rest of the supply chain. Latency creates space or allowance of unexpected or unpredicted change to emerge; in other words, there is no a-priori agreement that firms enact with respect to specific business model changes. The firms instead agree on a particular outcome and allow the requisite changes to take place for the realization of that outcome. Because of this, there is no leader-follower dichotomy in the digital transformation of a supply chain, but a focal firm that facilitates and leads the digital transformation (Foss et al., 2023; Snihur et al., 2018). Further, as each firm in the supply chain reacts to a business model change, they adapt their own efforts and operations in real time. There is a back-and-forth shifting, which allows firms to calibrate with one another to optimize their unique contributions to value creation in the emergent digital ecosystem. Thus, interlinked firms in a supply chain do not change their business models simultaneously or sequentially; rather, they do so in curvilinear ways adapting and reacting until a mutuality and complementarity is established among supply chain firms. The figures 3-4 illustrate the cyclical relationship between latency and emergence, demonstrating how early-stage, non-economic transformations set the foundation for subsequent economic gains. Latency-driven initiatives, such as utilizing genetic data for cattle healthcare (T1), forming partnerships with dairy farms (T5 – T6) pave the way for tangible economic benefits, including increased capital investment (T9), the franchising of KN to other farms (T7 – T8), and the production of high-end products (T8).

Findings reveal that a key enabler of this transformation is real-time data synchronization, which enhances coordination across system-level efforts (Hafeez et al., 2025; Herterich et al., 2023; Rantala et al., 2023), including data-driven healthcare, standardized feeding practices, and visibility-enhanced trading mechanisms. As digital transformation progresses, these elements work together to drive continuous improvements in economic efficiency and BMC. At the heart of this process is data-sharing, interoperability, portability and leveraging real-time linked-data to improve the farming efficiency and profitability, which serves as a crucial market enabler. Rantala et al. (2023) echoes the same notion and mentions that data driven decisions reduce the liability of newness in an ecosystem and facilitate BMC and new partnerships. The figures highlight how firms transition from establishing data infrastructure (T0-T2) to fully leveraging shared data for ecosystem-wide benefits (T8-T10). This transition not only improves investment returns and operational efficiencies but also enables product differentiation and value capture through premium pricing models. Moreover, the monetization of data streams through data-as-a-service models (T10) reinforces the economic sustainability of digital transformation, demonstrating how firms within the ecosystem evolve from merely exchanging information to strategically leveraging data as a core business asset.

Critically, latency and emergence did not act independently but in tandem, reinforcing each other throughout the transformation. Early latency established essential trust, transparency, and infrastructure, while emergence rapidly leveraged these foundations for immediate economic and strategic gains across ecosystem participants. This cycle - latent groundwork followed by emergent economic realization - was continuously evident throughout the study period (T0 to T10), mirroring and reinforcing theoretical perspectives introduced earlier in the manuscript regarding latency as necessary groundwork for emergent economic recalibrations.

Overall, the interplay between latency and emergence coordinated business model changes not through hierarchical control but via a co-evolutionary and collaborative adaptation process, continually informed and reinforced by shared real-time data. This highlights a core theoretical

insight: the digital transformation of a supply chain into a digital ecosystem relies fundamentally on the integrated action of latency-driven foundational developments and emergence-driven economic synchronization.

Insert Figure 3 here

Insert Figure 4 here

In short, the findings explain how real-time data synchronization acts as a vital component, enhancing coordination and driving efficiency. Firms transition from building data capabilities to using shared data for widespread benefits, including new revenue streams. Importantly, this transformation is not top-down but a collaborative evolution where initial groundwork and emerging economic gains mutually reinforce each other.

6. Theoretical Implications

There are several important theoretical implications regarding the interplay of latency and emergence, the role of data, and the nature of digital ecosystem transformation. First, the cyclical relationship between latency and emergence implies that sustainable economic gains in a digital ecosystem are built upon a foundation of early-stage, often non-economic, initiatives. This suggests that organizations and ecosystems looking to achieve significant economic benefits through digital transformation must first invest in foundational elements like establishing SOPs, forming partnerships, and building data infrastructure and trust. These "latency-driven initiatives" are not immediately profitable but are essential prerequisites for future "emergent" economic successes such as increased investment, franchising, and premium product offerings. This cycle suggests that a long-term perspective and a willingness to invest in foundational, non-immediately revenue-generating activities are crucial for successful digital transformation (Hanelt et al., 2021).

Second, the findings emphasize the role of data as a key enabler and driver of digital transformation (Chae, 2019; Wu et al., 2024). Real-time data synchronization facilitates coordination across various system-level efforts, including healthcare, feeding practices, and trading mechanisms, leading to continuous improvements in economic efficiency and business model change (Sengupta et al., 2021; Weking et al., 2020). Furthermore, data sharing is presented as a crucial market enabler, allowing firms to move from establishing data infrastructure to leveraging shared data for ecosystem-wide benefits. This not only enhances investment returns and operational efficiencies but also enables product differentiation and value capture through premium pricing. The evolution towards monetizing data streams through data-as-a-service models underscores the strategic importance of data as a core business asset within a mature digital ecosystem. This implies that organizations should prioritize building robust data infrastructures, fostering data-sharing mechanisms, and developing capabilities for leveraging data insights to unlock economic value.

Finally, the interplay between latency and emergence orchestrates business model changes not through traditional hierarchical control but through a co-evolutionary and collaborative adaptation process. This process is continuously informed and reinforced by shared real-time data. This implication suggests that digital ecosystem transformation is a dynamic and decentralized

process, relying on the collective adaptation and collaboration of its participants rather than distinct top-down directives. Organizations need to embrace a more flexible and collaborative approach to business model change, leveraging shared data to drive continuous improvement and adaptation across the ecosystem. Ultimately, the digital transformation of a supply chain into a digital ecosystem fundamentally relies on the integrated action of latency-driven foundational developments and emergence-driven economic synchronization. Neither latency nor emergence can independently deliver a successful transformation; they must work in tandem, with early groundwork enabling rapid economic realization. This highlights the interdependence of foundational and economic aspects of digital transformation. Neglecting either aspect can hinder the overall progress and potential benefits of the transformation.

In essence, successful digital ecosystem transformation is a temporal dual mechanism of latency and emergence which realizes collective business model change and consequent ecosystem emergence. The focal firms' latent investments enable distributed emergence across the ecosystem through a strategic focus on data as a core asset, a collaborative and adaptive mindset, and a recognition of the interconnectedness between early-stage groundwork and subsequent economic gains.

7. Managerial Implications

This study offers several critical managerial insights for leaders navigating business model transformation from a physical supply chain to a digital ecosystem. Most importantly, it underscores how business models evolve dynamically at the ecosystem level rather than merely within isolated firms. Specifically, our findings highlight that successful transformation depends heavily on the careful orchestration of latency: foundational, non-economic groundwork - and emergence: economic recalibration triggered by this groundwork.

Initially, managers must recognize and embrace the role of latency, particularly when transitioning from traditional physical supply chain activities toward a digitally-integrated ecosystem. Early digital initiatives, such as developing comprehensive cattle data repositories, standardized animal healthcare practices, and smart logistics solutions, may not produce immediate economic returns but instead facilitate essential collaborative complexity. Such latent actions gradually build the infrastructure and institutional trust necessary for later emergent economic gains. Subsequently, the process of emergence demonstrates how economic recalibrations across multiple stakeholders are catalyzed by real-time data synchronization and continuous feedback loops within the evolving ecosystem. This means that managers must prioritize digital transformation initiatives not just as discrete technology investments, but as integrated activities connecting firms through data-driven adjustments. As such, digital transformation from a physical supply chain to a digital ecosystem relies significantly on creating conditions where multiple actors can co-evolve, driven by data-sharing and reciprocal responsiveness, ultimately facilitating mutual economic benefit.

Critically, our findings reveal that ecosystem-level digital transformation is not centrally controlled but involves an adaptive, curvilinear interplay between latency and emergence. Managers must therefore abandon rigid, firm-centric strategic frameworks in favour of flexible leadership and facilitation, encouraging ecosystem participants to co-create shared solutions based on increasingly granular and customized data. Such an approach leverages latency-driven initiatives, such as standardized operational procedures and proactive partnership formation, as critical steps towards subsequent emergent economic outcomes.

The initiative of *SaaS* was introduced to standardize digital farming operations and *Data as a Service* to deliver analytics and compliance tools for regulators. To improve livestock productivity, *Customized Feed Supply as a Service* offered tailored nutrition solutions, while *Infrastructure as a Service* enabled shared investment in smart farming setups. To build human capital, *Training as a Service* delivered digital upskilling programs for local labor. Smart Logistics enhanced transportation through digital coordination, and the Franchising Business Model supported regional scaling through partner expansion. Consistency across operations was ensured through *SOP as a Service*, offering standardized guidelines. Strategic R&D Farms acted as hubs for process innovation and IP generation, while multi-sided trading platforms fostered transparent, equitable interaction among farmers, traders, service providers, and financial actors. Finally, *Financial Services leveraging Digital Twins* allowed livestock data to serve as financial assets, unlocking access to credit and insurance. Together, these models (as shown in Figure 5) represent a digitally integrated, inclusive, and scalable smart farming ecosystem grounded in collaboration, innovation, and financial empowerment.

Finally, recognizing the ongoing real-life impact since 2021, our research further facilitated the development of a Direct-to-Consumer (D2C) model through launching retail outlets such as branded restaurants. Leveraging comprehensive digital infrastructures and high-quality ecosystem data, this approach facilitates direct connection to end-consumers, enabling greater value capture, brand differentiation, and market expansion.

In essence, managers aiming to realize sustained competitive advantage through digital transformation must strategically manage the interplay of latency and emergence, making careful foundational investments, data-driven collaboration, and adaptive leadership, allowing business models to continuously evolve across interconnected stakeholders.

Insert Figure 5 here

8. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Like any study this research also has certain limitations that future studies can address. While the study spans a 10-year period, capturing the formation of an ecosystem and its microfoundations for a focal firm and its business partners, the insights are derived specifically from a beef farming supply chain. This contextual focus may limit the generalizability of the findings to other sectors, such as manufacturing supply chains. Additionally, although the study emphasizes the critical role of a visionary in steering ecosystem evolution, it does not delve into the specific characteristics or attributes of the visionary firm itself an area that warrants further exploration. Finally, the study centres on understanding the underlying mechanisms of digital transformation within an ecosystem, particularly highlighting the significance of data sharing. However, it does not examine the equally important dimension of data privacy, specifically, how individual firms within the ecosystem safeguard their data. In the digital era, the establishment of clear rules and standards around data sharing and privacy is a critical factor that future research should explore in greater depth.

Several promising avenues for future research emerge from this study, particularly around exploring the dynamic interplay of latency and emergence in diverse contexts and industries. While our findings are based on a longitudinal analysis of the beef farming industry in China and Southeast Asia, further research should examine whether and how these latency-emergence cycles

operate across other supply chains, such as manufacturing, healthcare, or services, to enhance generalizability and understand industry-specific contingencies.

Moreover, future research should delve deeper into the role and characteristics of visionary leaders who facilitate ecosystem-level digital transformation. While this study recognizes visionaries as crucial catalysts for latency and emergence, more empirical work is needed to unpack specific leadership attributes, strategic decision-making processes, and managerial practices that enable visionaries to navigate the complexity inherent in ecosystem-level transformations effectively. Additionally, our findings raise important questions regarding optimal governance structures for digital ecosystems. Future research might explore how governance mechanisms, such as multi-sided platforms, joint ventures, and collaborative alliances, influence latency and emergence dynamics, particularly in managing risks and distributing benefits equitably among diverse stakeholders. Investigating governance models and their effectiveness in different ecosystems and institutional contexts could yield vital insights for managers and policymakers seeking sustainable, inclusive digital transformation.

Moreover, given the rising prominence of data sharing and digital infrastructure, future studies should investigate the risks and challenges associated with ecosystem-level data governance, including privacy, cybersecurity, data ownership, and equitable benefit distribution from shared data resources. These insights would help managers and policymakers establish robust frameworks to ensure responsible and equitable data-driven transformations.

Finally, future research should explicitly examine the triple-bottom-line impacts (economic, environmental, and social) of digital ecosystem transformations. Specifically, further investigation could assess how the emerging business models identified in this study such as SFaaS, Data as a Service, customized feed solutions, and franchising models contribute to environmental and social sustainability. This includes evaluating the direct and indirect impacts on carbon neutrality, waste reduction, community employment, and regional economic development. Critically, studies should adopt a systematic approach to assess how digital ecosystem transformations simultaneously impact economic profitability, environmental sustainability, and social equity, offering managers a holistic understanding of how to balance trade-offs among these outcomes.

Table 3 Details of initiatives and associated changes (First order codes)

Changes Phases	Restructuring Initiatives	Supply Chain changes	Business Model Changes	Ecosystem Changes
<p>Strategic foresight and Diagnosis (T0 → T2)</p>	<p>Analysis of micro-environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of traceability for cattle information • Lack of breeding technology and breeding volumes • Lower survival and meat yield rates • Inefficient healthcare practices • Lack of finances and economic gain for farmers • Intuition based decisions and pricing for trading and sales • Power asymmetries among abattoirs, traders and farmers 	<p>Develop tenets of Digital Transformation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared centralized database developed to record cattle pedigree • Development of protocols for biometric-based healthcare • Planning digitized trading processes (non-executed yet) • Initial data feedback loops to evaluate cattle feed effectiveness • Integration of predictive healthcare into treatment schedules 	<p>Value Proposition: Trusted, digitised identity and health data for each animal; initial push toward predictive health.</p> <p>Value Capture: No direct monetization; investment-focused stage with high infrastructure costs.</p> <p>Value chain Partners: Core KN team; technical partners for data infrastructure; integrated healthcare providers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early actors aligned via shared goals but no interdependence yet • Knowledge silos exist; minimal external engagement
<p>Capability formation and Strategic Platformization (T3 → T5)</p>	<p>Shared Digital Infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocation of resources for foundational ICT capacity building • Digitizing the trading process • Platformization (One sided → Multisided) <p>Systemic Synchronization through Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint ventures formed with feed suppliers and logistics firms (T1) • Infrastructure alignment for cattle ID and traceability (T2) • Smart transportation initiated to monitor cattle during commute (T3) • Co-development of digital SOPs for feed, health, and trade (T3 – T5) 	<p>Platform driven Relational Capital</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One-sided trading platform developed • Standardized data driven trading and pricing based on cattle data quality • Feed purchase and patterns optimized based on genetics and growth data • Feed customization using real-time biometric data • Feed trading company formed • Development of smart trucks embedded with sensors • Logistics providers partner with traders to provide service to other farms as well • Multisided platform developed 	<p>Value Proposition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product-based offerings to service-oriented value • Emergence of standardized, transparent trading systems • Reduced asymmetries and power imbalance • Development of data-informed services, creating performance-based differentiation • Integrated service models across feeding, trading, and logistics, offering seamless farm-to-abattoir coordination. • Economic equity for farmers. <p>Value Capture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a multi-sided platform as a relational infrastructure. • Lower operational costs via virtual business development and reduced on-ground interaction. 	<p>Product differentiation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of healthcare providers as formal nodes in the digital supply chain. • Data sharing enables cross-functional decisions (e.g., traders rely on health data, feed optimized based on medical history). • Improved trust between actors due to shared, standardized health data. <p>Ecosystem Emergence through Partner Inclusion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal inclusion of feed, logistics, and trading partners • Multi-sided participation emerging through shared data loops • Weak ties transforming into dense relational interdependence • Ecosystem-wide transparency begins to influence practices

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversified income streams through new ventures and formalize service delivery • Partners embedded within the broader supply chain via digital systems. • Monetizing Infrastructure – revenue from multisided platform <p>Value Chain Partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traders, logistics, healthcare providers, and farmers. 	
<p>Ecosystem Emergence and Institutionalization (T6 → T9)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Franchising of KN smart farm model via joint ventures (T5 –T7) • SOP development for farm operations, tech handling, and service customization (T6) • Training SOPs and mobile teams created for farm replication (T6) • KN branding expanded to dairy and breeding farms (T7 – T8) • Launch of SFaaS consultancy and training firm (T8) • Financial product co-design with banks using DT cattle as collateral (T9) • Data monetization and sustainability consulting for government and trade bodies (T9–T10) • Launch of a flagship R&D smart farm to license IP and refine ecosystem service portfolio (T9 - T10) • Data monetization architecture and IP protection measures deployed (T10) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supply-demand linkage via franchising smart farms (T6–T7) • Standardization of breeding, feeding, and healthcare practices across farms (T8) • Integration with dairy supply chains for premium products and increased cross-sectoral synergies (T8b, T8d) • Smart feed logistics and infrastructure reuse (T6–T8) • Feedback loops enhanced for predictive and prescriptive insights • Partnership with construction companies to build farms • Partnership with DT installation company responsible for modification of farms into a smart farm • Data demand from government • Consumer demand from retail for high beef quality and traceability • High demand from end consumers – D2C initiated 	<p>Value Proposition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized farm set up and breeding services (T6) • Circularity: Transforming dairy waste into beef revenue (T8b) • Data-as-a-Service: Regulatory compliance, carbon tracking, standard-setting (T8–T10) • Retail product (high end restaurant) • Licensing & IP creation from flagship farm trials (T10) <p>Value Capture:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared ownership of farms, dividend-based returns for construction firms (T6) • Royalties from franchised farms (T7–T9) • Revenue from SFaaS training programs for local authorities and rural subsidies (T8 – T9) • Sale of digital assets (data, sustainability metrics, certification services) to policy and industry bodies (T9–T10) • Licensing of R&D-based innovations and standards (T10) <p>Value Chain Partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traders, farmers, feed suppliers, logistics firms, healthcare providers, end consumers and regulatory bodies. 	<p>Modular Replication of Value Models</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion from a beef-focused platform to an integrated agri-food ecosystem • Entry of adjacent sector actors (dairy, breeding, retail, government, banks) • Platform legitimacy strengthened via data-backed creditworthiness and sustainability compliance (T6 – T8) <p>Data Monetization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalization of digital standards influencing national policy (T8–T9) • KN sells data-driven services to franchises, local farms, governing bodies and • Cross-industry orchestration and resource circularity (e.g., dairy-breeding-beef integrations) • Emergence of KN as a governance actor setting benchmarks for the broader ecosystem (T9 – T10)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of specialist service partners (e.g., digital twin installers, smart farm construction company, TMR feed firms, smart truck manufacturers) to support capability building 	
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Table 4. Digital Transformation of a Supply Chain to a Digital Ecosystem (second order)

Issues from a Supply Chain Perspective	Before Digital Transformation T(-1)	After Digital Transformation T(14)	Role of Digital Twins	Opportunities from a Digital Ecosystem Perspective
Heterogeneity and uncertainty regarding inputs / supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of systematic breeding technology Scarce breeding base for cattle in the market Non standardized beef – difficult to manage Lack of stable cattle source 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> KN cattle is taller, heavier, and smoother in coat colour Cattle are more standardized, making it easy to manage Smart pasture with scientific breeding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information standardization and clustering through cattle data uploaded by franchise cattle dealers Ground personnel verifying the authenticity of standardized information 	Shared authenticated data empowers firms to trust and coordinate with one another
Lack of quality control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inefficient disease and control prevention systems Traditional govt vaccines Low survival rate of cows Poor growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data driven healthcare based on pedigree record Additional vaccines personalized based on cattle and pedigree records Survival rate increased more than 97% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real time monitoring Database for cattle maintained Feed and healthcare administered as per data as opposed to “one size fits all” 	Real-time data synchronizes system-level efforts to improve product quality
Inefficient logistics and transportation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inefficient transportation of cattle leading to weight loss and infections 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Special vehicle logistics Smart trucks developed for cattle commute 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart trucks with feedlots embedded Water intake ensured at intervals during commute Computer vision to monitor stress of cattle 	Data streamlines logistics, making it possible for multiple firms to support successful transportation

<p>Lack of trust, purely transactional exchange</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intuition based trading • Judgements based on expert intuition and naked eye • Broker as a middleman earning undue commission giving the farmer a financial hit • Lack of farmer motivation to improve production • Sales done by price per head rather than price per kg – giving farmer low economic yield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KN platform for trading established • Cattle dealers and farmers complying to franchise standards on the platform • Non-compliant parties restricted • regular online professional training for franchisees and occasional offline guidance meetings led by franchisees • matching "buyer clusters" and "cattle information clusters" 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trading platform with cattle record visible to all traders and farmers • Platform extended to include other stakeholders to facilitate commute and other activities • Transparency in trading • Data driven decisions with economic equality for all partners 	<p>Platform-based model facilitates trust, relational exchange, and mutuality</p>
<p>Insufficient production capacity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of finances to expand production • Cattle dealers and retail investors short of money • Lack of customer groups • Insufficient production capacity at fattening plants due to low breeding volume 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments facilitated through new business model • Local authority involvement in training as a means of revenue • Banks involved in the business model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KN established SFaaS Consulting company • Training as a service established as a separate company • banks use the DT as an asset to issue financial product by the bank to investors • Legitimize KNs asset – herds • Reduce their own investments – transferred the cost centre 	<p>Stronger stakeholder engagement in ecosystem leads to more resources and improved capabilities</p>
<p>Low profit margins, Value capture based on volume</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low conversion rate of meat to higher grade beef (A2, A3) • Problem in depositing fat into cow muscles between 16 – 22 months • Insufficient quality checks in industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical guidance of cattle established 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing and Selling comprehensive standards for beef farming across the value chain • Based on genetics and data records, more customized feeding and growth of cattle to yield high grade beef 	<p>Shared data facilitates product differentiation, value capture based on higher price</p>

<p>Inconsistent and costly negotiation per transaction</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terminal sales price of cattle at abattoir is low • Cow value measured by meat and no means of ensuring transparency in meat value from abattoir • Unspoken rule by abattoirs to artificially lower the cattle price • 2 yuan per kg per cow difference increased to 4 yuan • Results in lower sales value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased earnings per cattle unit, lower overall costs, improved overall quality of cattle. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setting different age-related weight standards and through pricing systems • KNs automatic weighing system can be linked with cattle quality and verified by the ground team to improve the quality of cattle 	<p>Shared data improves return on investment for all firms in the ecosystem</p>
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Figure 1. Coding for Latency in the Ecosystem

Figure 2. Coding for Emergence in the Ecosystem

Figure 3. Cyclical Interplay of Latency-Emergence at the Ecosystem Level and Firm-Level Business Model Change in a Digital Ecosystem

Figure 4. Navigating Digital Transformation

Figure 5. Digitally Integrated Scalable Smart Farming Ecosystem

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